

**AN ANALYSIS STUDY ON THE EFFECT OF FINANCIAL LEVERAGE ON
PROFITABILITY OF THE SELECTED AUTOMOBILE COMPANIES
FROM THE NIFTY FIFTY**

Dabhi Shailesh Natubhai

Research Scholar, Department of Commerce & Management
Bhakta Kavi Narsinh Mehta University Junagadh-362263, Gujarat, India

Abstract

The automobile industry is most important role in economic development and transportation systems worldwide. The primary purpose of the research work is to evaluate the effect of leverage on profitability from selected Indian automobile companies. The top five companies choose for this study are Bajaj Auto Ltd, Eicher Motors Ltd, Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd, Maruti Suzuki India Ltd and Tata Motors Ltd based on NIFTY 50. The study is covering a period of 5 years 2021-22 to 2025-26. In analysing the leverage and profitability position, financial leverage is considered the independent variable while earning per share is considered the outcome variable. The study examines how changes in financial leverage affect EPS. For the results concluded that Bajaj Auto Ltd and Eicher Motors Ltd Financial leverage and EPS have a negative relationship. In Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd, Maruti Suzuki India Ltd and Tata Motors Ltd, Financial leverage and EPS have a negative relationship. Regression analysis found that there is no effect of financial leverage on earning per share in BNL and EML but in M&M, MSIL and TML financial leverage has significant impact on EPS.

Keywords: *Leverage, Profitability, Earning Per Share, Automobile, Nifty 50*

Introduction

The automobile industry is among the leading sectors contributing to economic growth and industrial development. It includes the manufacturing and production of vehicles such as cars, motorcycles, buses and commercial vehicles. Automobile companies play important role in transportation, technological advancement, employee generation and improve the standard living. The automobile industry is currently experiencing rapid growth due to advance technological, changing market demand, consumer awareness and the increasing use of Artificial intelligence. In modern technology adopted in automobiles industry such as Artificial intelligence, Electric Vehicles (EVs), automation and smart technologies. Companies are adopting innovative technologies to improve efficiency, customer satisfaction and market competitiveness.

Financial decisions are an important part of business management because they affect the company's capital structure, cost of capital and overall financial performance. Leverage helps to analysis thus debt-equity

relationship and its effect on the company's performance and shareholder's returns. It shows change in sales or financing decision can affect EBIT and EPS. A higher level of leverage may increase returns but it also increases financial risk. It must however be noted that higher the level of leverage, higher is the risk along with return to the owners.

Review of Literature

Meghanathi & Chakrawal (2023), has conducted research on the topic of "Leverage'-An Analysis and its Impact on Profitability with Reference to Selected Oil and Gas Companies in India" The purpose of the study was to examine the impact of leverage on the profitability of selected Companies in India. In this research paper based on secondary data have been collected from 5 years cover a period of the year 2016-17 to 2020-21. The study was selected top five oil and gas companies based on market capitalization. In this study researcher found that there is no influencing of financial leverage on eps in RIL, ONGC and IOCL but in BPCL and GAIL financial leverage has influencing on EPS.

Sultana (2018), have conducted research on the title of "An Analysis of Financial Ratios Impact on Profitability of Select Automobile Companies in India." In this study objective was to evaluate the impact of Profitability on Liquidity ratio and Leverage ratios. The study was covered a period of 5 years from the year 2012 to 2016. In this paper selected 7 company from Nifty 50 companies. In this study the result conclude that Debit Equity ratio & Debtors Turnover Ratio are impact on Net profit margin of selected companies and also impact of Liquidity ratio on Capital Employed & Return on Net Worth of the selected automobile companies.

Arts (2020), has studied the "Leverage – An Analysis and its Impact on Profitability with Reference to Selected Fertilizer Companies in India" The main object of the research work is to understand and examine the leverage effects on profitability of the selected private sector fertilizers companies. The study was covered a period of 10 years from the year 2006 to 2015. This study is based on the secondary data collected from the annual reports and accounts of the selected company. The researcher found that Chambal fertilizer, khaitan Fertilizer and Mangalore fertilizer ltd are highly leveraged companies. company is using nearby 70% borrowed fund on the other hand GSFC Ltd is low leveraged company.

Jethwa (2015), has conducted research on the topic of "a study on operating leverage of automobile companies from NIFTY 50" The main object of the research paper is to know the level of operating leverage of automobile companies falling in the list of Nifty 50. In this research work based on data from secondary published sources. This study selected five automobile companies in the list of Nifty- 50 index. The researcher found that the study that companies year on year basis do follow pattern but there is no similarity found between these companies and this is because companies differ in age, size and its presence in the international market which affects the level of operating leverage.

Ahuja & Gupta (2019), has conducted research on the topic “Impact of financial leverage on the financial performance of selected automobile companies”. The major goal of the research work to investigated the impact of financial leverage measures on firm's performance. In this study was carried out on top five listed companies in 2018 taken from different segments of automobile sector in India. The study was covered a period of 5 years from the year 2014 to 2018. In this financial leverage and performance examine ratios like Debt Ratio (DR), Debt Equity Ratio (DER), Interest Coverage Ratio (ICR). The researcher concluded that research is a significant association between financial leverage and profitability of the firm, its means financial leverage has positive effect on profitability and efficiency of companies.

Methods

The Research Methodology is a systematic process of identifying problem and drawing conclusion to achieve the objective of the study.

Objectives

This study analysed the following objectives;

- 1) To analyses the leverage position of selected Indian automobile companies
- 2) To analyse profitability performance of selected Indian automobile companies.
- 3) To evaluate the association between leverage and profitability of selected units.
- 4) To measure the effect of leverage on profitability of selected Indian automobile companies.

Hypotheses

H₀ = There is no significant difference in financial leverage of selected Indian automobile companies during the research work.

H₀ = There is no significant difference in Earning Per Share among selected Indian automobile companies during the research work.

H₀ = There is no significant association between financial leverage and earning per share of selected Indian automobile companies during the research work.

H₀ = There is no significant effect of financial leverage on earning per share of selected Indian automobile companies during the research work.

Period

The period of the research work has been considered 5 years from 2021-22 to 2025-26.

Scope

For the study scope have been divided in to two parts first one is functional scope and second one is geographical scope.

Functional Scope: Functional scope of the research work has been considered as leverage and profitability analysis for selected automobile companies from NIFTY 50 in India. For the identification of leverage and profitability, the study was divided into two segments, namely profitability ratios and leverage ratios and the respective ratios were selected.

Geographical Scope: The study has been limited to India, considering the selected automobile companies from the NIFTY 50 index operating within the Indian economic environment.

Selection of Samples: The study sample use five automobile companies based on top from the NIFTY 50 index.

Sr. No	Name of Company
1.	Bajaj Auto Ltd.
2.	Eicher Motors Ltd.
3.	Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.
4.	Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.
5.	Tata Motors Ltd.

Data Collection: This study secondary source of data has collected from annual report of the company along with respective websites of the companies

Financial Leverage

Year	BJL	EML	M&M	MSIL	TML
2021-22	0	0	0.17	0.01	1.17
2022-23	0	0	0.11	0.02	0.84
2023-24	0.03	0.01	0.03	0	0.46
2024-25	0.02	0.01	0.02	0	0.26
2025-26	0	0.01	0.01	0	0.09
AVG	0.01	0.006	0.068	0.006	0.564
MAX	0.03	0.01	0.17	0.02	1.17
MIN	0	0	0.01	0	0.09

Source: www.moneycontrol.com

Above table show the financial leverage of automobile selected companies for the period of 2021-22 to 2025-26. Financial leverage is the percentage of debt as compared to the owner's equity in capital structure of the company. In Bajaj Auto Ltd. the average financial leverage is 0.01, maximum is 0.03 in the year 2023-24 and minimum is 0 in the year 2021-22 and also 2022-23. In the year 2023-24 the debt proportion is highest in Bajaj Auto Ltd. And 3 years have no dept. In Eicher Motors Ltd. Dept ratios was 0 in the year of 2021 to 23 then continuously low at 0.01 in 2023-24 to 2025-26 years. In Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd. Continuously decrease in 2021-25-26 and the average financial leverage is 0.068. In Maruti Suzuki India Ltd. maximum financial leverage is 0.02 in the year 2022-23 it shows higher the debt compared to owner's fund. In Tata

Motors Ltd. the average financial leverage is .564 is highest compared to all the other selected companies it showed higher debt percentage in the company.

Earnings Per Share

Year	BJL	EML	M&M	MSIL	TML
2021-22	173.6	48.68	41.28	124.68	-3.63
2022-23	197.3	58.02	54.7	266.46	7.11
2023-24	264.6	95.91	89.42	431.08	20.61
2024-25	292.1	136.98	98.8	443.86	15.44
2025-26	352	156.15	130.18	459.46	14.26
AVG	255.92	99.148	82.876	345.108	10.758
MAX	352	156.15	130.18	459.46	20.61
MIN	173.6	48.68	41.28	124.68	-3.63

Source: www.moneycontrol.com

Above table indicated the Earning Per Share of selected automobile companies during the research work. Earnings per share (EPS) is the portion of company's profit that is allocated to every individual share of the stock. In Bajaj Auto Ltd. the average eps are 255.92, Highest eps are 352 in the year 2025-26 and lowest in the year 2021-22. In Eicher Motors Ltd. Continuously increase eps from 2021-22 to 2025-26. In Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd the average eps are 82.876 and maximum 130.18 in 2025-26 year and minimum 41.28 in 2021-22 year. In Maruti Suzuki India Ltd. the average eps are 345.108 it shows highest average eps compared to another firm. In Tata Motors Ltd. showed the zig-zag trend of EPS and negative EPS in the 2021-22. Its show the average lowest eps in another firms.

One-Way Anova

Ratio	F- Value	F- Crit	P-Value	H0 Accept / Reject
Financial Leverage	12.56986	2.641465	1.93E-06	H0 Rejected
Earnings Per Share	24.03676	2.641465	1.26E-09	H0 Rejected

Source: Calculated from MS Excel

Above table shows of the one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for financial leverage and earning per share. In financial leverage calculated value (12.56986) is higher than table value (2.641465) it is indicated that the rejection of the null hypothesis at 5% level of significance means that there is significant change in financial leverage of selected Indian automobile companies during the research work. In Earning Per Share (EPS) also the calculate value (24.03676) is higher than table value (2.641465) it shows that that the rejection of the null hypothesis at 5% level of significance means that there is a significant change in Earning Per Share among selected Indian automobile companies during the research work.

Correlation of Financial Leverage with Earning Per Share

Companies	Correlation	Results
BJL	0.539123	Positive
EML	0.911589	Positive
M&M	-0.1149	Negative
MSIL	-0.08411	Negative
TML	-0.03249	Negative

Source: Calculated from MS Excel

Above table shows that the correlation of financial leverage with earning per share. In Bajaj Auto Ltd, Eicher Motors Ltd are shows positive association between financial leverage with EPS but not much significant. It means financial leverage and earning per share have a direct relationship. It means when Financial Leverage increases, EPS also tends to increases. In other cases, companies show the result of correlation is negative it shows there is negative relationship between financial leverage with EPS, it means financial leverage and Earning Per Share move in opposite directions. It means an increases financial leverage tends to decreases Earning Per Share.

Regression Analysis

Companies	Coefficients	Standard Error	T Stat	P-value	5 % significant level	H0 Accept/Reject
BJL	2882.796	1838.569	1.567957	0.167938	0.05	Accepted
EML	8445.536	1554.897	5.431571	0.001615	0.05	Rejected
M&M	-60.2529	212.6736	-0.28331	0.786459	0.05	Accepted
MSIL	-1374.39	6647.283	-0.20676	0.843036	0.05	Accepted
TML	-0.7118	8.937962	-0.07964	0.939115	0.05	Accepted

Source: Calculated from MS Excel

Above table shows the regression analysis of selected Indian automobile companies during the research work. As per the above table in BJJ, M&M, MSIL and YML the P-value is higher than 0.05 at 5% significant level so, null hypothesis is not rejected. It means that there is no effect observed of financial leverage on EPS of above four companies during the study period. The standard error of BJJ, EML, M&M, MSIL and TML was found to be 1838.569, 1554.897, 212.6736, 6647.283, and 8.937962 respectively. In the companies EML the P-value is lower than 0.05 at 5% significant level so the null hypothesis is not accepted. It means that there is a effect observed of financial leverage on EPS of company during the research work.

Conclusion

The research findings of ANOVA test shows that there is significant differences in financial leverage and earning per share of selected Indian automobile companies during research work. In Bajaj Auto Ltd and Eicher Motors Ltd Financial leverage and EPS move in the same direction. If the company increases debt, EPS may also increase, but the effect is not significant. In the same way if company reduce its debt than EPS also decrease but not significant. In Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd, Maruti Suzuki India Ltd and Tata Motors Ltd,

Financial leverage and EPS have a negative relationship. It means that when financial leverage increases, Earning Per Share decreases. In the same way if company reduce its debt than EPS also increases but significant. In Regression analysis discovered that only Eicher Motors Ltd company showed a rejected result, indicated that financial leverage has no effect on Earning Per Share (EPS). However, the remaining companies showed accepted results, indicated that financial leverage has a significant effect on Earning Per Share (EPS). In correlation analysis found that BJL and EML companies are showed a positive association between financial leverage and EPS other companies showed a negative effect between financial leverage and EPS.

References

- Ahuja, J., & Gupta, A. (2019). *IMPACT OF FINANCIAL LEVERAGE ON THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED AUTOMOBILE COMPANIES*.
- Arts, J. Z. S. (2020). 'Leverage' – An Analysis and its Impact on Profitability with Reference to Selected Private Sector Fertilizer Companies in India.
- Jethwa, D. D. (2015). *A STUDY ON OPERATING LEVERAGE OF AUTOMOBILE COMPANIES FROM NIFTY-50*.
- Meghanathi, P. D., & Chakrawal, A. K. (2023). Leverage'–An Analysis and its Impact on Profitability with Reference to Selected Oil and Gas Companies in India. *Journal La Bisecoman*, 3(4), 133–139. <https://doi.org/10.37899/journallabisecoman.v3i4.777>
- Sultana, D. S. T. (2018). *AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL RATIOS IMPACT ON PROFITABILITY OF SELECT AUTOMOBILE COMPANIES IN INDIA*. 8.
- Majhi, D. P. (2017). *Research Methodology*. New Delhi: Himalaya Publishing House
- S.S VINOD CHANDRA, S. A. (2017). *Research Methodology*. (P. K. Bhattacharjee, Ed.) Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India: Pearson India Education Services Pvt. Ltd.
- SONDHI, D. C. (2018). *Research Methodology*. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House Pvt Ltd.
- Dolald R. Copper, P. S. (2003). *Business Research Methods*. New York: Mc-Graw Hill Publication.
- J.K., S. (2014). *Business Statistic*. UP (India): Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
- Madaan, K. V. (2019). *Teaching And Research Aptitude*. Noida: Pearson Publications.
- Dr.Tulsian P. C "Financial Management", New Delhi, S. Chand & Company Ltd.,2009 2nd Adition.
- M.Y. Khan & P.K. Jain. *Financial Management* (Tata McGraw Hill, Publishers) 4thEdition.
- Sanjeev Kumar. (2013). "*Financial Management*" Thakur publisher pvt. 1st edition 6th March 2013.
- I.M pandey, (2013). *Financial Management*", Vikas publishing house pvt. Ltd 9th edition 2013.